

Design and development of designer immunoglobulins for discovery-based therapeutic targeting.

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Linear epitope prediction for epitope-based recombinant immunoglobulin expression for use as a monoclonal antibody reagent.

1. We first identified epitopes for therapeutic targets of interest, linear or otherwise, using computational epitope prediction.

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2. We used VSTM2L as a model protein for design and expression of recombinant, rationally designed immunoglobulins.

- a. Linear epitope predictions for Igsf9b and Sftpa2 are also included.
- b. Igsf9b and Sftpa2 (Lung) and VSTM2L (CNS) are the three defined components of the CNS and Lung Metastasis immune activation regimens developed and being studied.

3. Seven linear epitopes with predicted residue scores were retrieved.

The first epitope predicted was a 35 amino acid sequence:

GGATRPAGHAPWDNHVSGHALFTETPHDMMTARTGE

4. Complementarity-determining regions (CDR) of heavy and light chains are selected through a blind bacteriophage screening approach with immobilized ligand of interest (the defined epitope).

- a. A second CDR discovery approach involves modeling of CDR antigen binding computationally with a defined antigen peptide.

5. We explored vector design, identifying a candidate vector backbone for recombinant heavy and light chain expression with Fab recognizing epitope of interest.

These included:

- a. A vector system for monoclonal antibody production with pre-defined epitope that involves co-expression of a cloned vector backbone expressing the cognate light chain and a cloned vector expressing the cognate heavy chain.

Commercial option: TGEX-FH-hG1-Zeo

Expresses the CH1 constant region of IgG1.

Co-transfection with TGEX-LC results in Ig Fab fragment production through co-expression of the light chain with the CH1 heavy chain sequence encoded by TGEX-FH-hG1-Zeo

- 1 b. Alternatively, immunoglobulin-like molecules that lack the Fc domain and instead contain only
2 variable regions of the heavy and light chains: single chain variable fragments, or scFv.
3 i. Here, a phage display system is used for scFv gene fragment selection, with a plate-based
4 bacteriophage peptide display for blind fragment clone selection.

5 Commercial option: TGEX-SCBLUE-Zeo-scFv Fc-VHH

6 5. We are currently identifying therapeutic targets for clinical use in multiple disease areas and developing
7 process-based systems to translate our basic discoveries. These processes include targeted
8 immunoglobulin expression and expedited drug approval schemes in patient populations that are eligible
9 for experimental drug administration under Compassionate Use protocols, like patients with metastatic
10 cancer that has failed available treatments.

11 6. Computational prediction of linear epitopes for design and recombinant expression of monoclonal
12 antibodies, identified using transcriptomics in primary tissues from humans with disease, will facilitate
13 rapid and safe clinical assessment of the viability of the developed monoclonal antibody and evaluation of
14 the reagent as a clinically efficacious therapeutic agent, maximizing potential for (or possibility of) clinical
15 efficacy through correct and complete target selection.

16 7. In human lymph node metastasis, the number of therapeutic targets we identified with confidence
17 across separate patient cohorts, whose mechanism of action and efficacy will be evaluated, translationally
18 in the laboratory and as a therapeutic agent in the clinic, approaches between 1,000-2,000 (the top 20%
19 most differentially expressed, up-regulated genes in the lymph node metastasis when compared
20 transcriptome-wide to the primary tumor).

21 8. Recombinant, rationally-designed immunoglobulin production will facilitate high-throughput study of
22 target efficacy and maximize likelihood for medical approval of a wide set of therapeutic targets whose
23 efficacy is already expected to be observed in the clinic based on study of human survival in cancer
24 patients, measuring survival (time in months) as a function of high or low tumor expression of the gene of
25 interest (the target identified) when comparing the high and low expression cohorts; we assume the low
26 expression group to resemble clinical phenotype associated with blockade of the molecule (target
27 inhibition) with a monoclonal antibody.
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Citations

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